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The Impact of Cross-Cultural Influences in Indian Printmaking

Parumeeta Sah

Research Scholar,
Department of Visual Arts,
Banasthali Vidyapith,
Rajasthan.

Dr. Manoj Kumar Tailor

Associate Professor,
Department of Visual Arts,
Banasthali Vidyapith,
Rajasthan.

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Abstract:

This paper analyses the profound impact of cross-cultural exchanges on the evolution of Indian printmaking and maps out its journey from ancient practices to contemporary expressions. Embodied in early symbolic carvings and religious imagery, Indian printmaking has been continuously shaped by global influences. The introduction of woodblock printing by Buddhist monks, followed by European colonial contributions to the cross-cultural element of printmaking, laid the groundwork for a rich artistic dialogue. Organisations like the Company School and Santiniketan became pivotal in blending Western techniques with Indian themes, fostering a unique aesthetic. The 20th century marked a distinct separation between printing and printmaking, which reflects the evolution of the artistic identity of Indian artists. With globalisation, Indian printmakers gained international visibility through exhibitions, biennales, and collaborations with various other countries. These interactions have diversified the medium while challenging traditional methods. This paper features how Indian printmaking stands today as a

dynamic fusion of heritage and innovation, navigating the balance between preserving age-old techniques and embracing modern technologies.

Keywords: Culture, Interaction, Hybrid Aesthetics, Printmaking, Techniques.

INTRODUCTION

The world of fine arts incorporates several disciplines, with painting, sculpture, and printmaking being the most prominent. Among these disciplines, printmaking requires a different level of technical expertise. When an artist walks on the journey of printmaking, they are involved in a process of experimentation, searching for the right combination of techniques to achieve a desired feeling. The work of printmaker is a manifestation of their inner thoughts and reflects their collective experiences. Printmaking is a technique in which an image or design is created by printing from a prepared surface, known as a matrix that holds ink and is transferred to a piece of paper or any other surface. The techniques that include this process are Relief, Intaglio, Planography, and Serigraphy. The differences among them lies in the image creation on the surface, how the surface is inked and what matrix is used and how the ink behaves when transferred to the paper.

Printmaking has a long and storied history in India. From the beginning, humans have required a medium to express their thoughts through reflection or communication. One of the earliest methods used by humans is to express themselves which has been through creating line drawings and figure drawings on cave walls and engravings, marking symbols on stone and prehistoric bones. That is among the oldest examples of the start of printmaking (Griffiths¹²). Art serves as a means to explore life through ancient lenses, embracing innovative and creative avenues, profound emotions, and influential ideologies.

The evolution of modern art reflects shifts in societal norms, behaviors, and interpersonal dynamics that leading to transformation in artistic expression (Ivins 41; Berger 21).

The history of Indian Printmaking has been marked by several key moments of cross-cultural exchange. Printmaking in India began in the early 20th century as an artistic medium; however, the practice of printmaking among artists was minimal until the 1950s (Goel and Singh 149). It has discovered that the use of wood blocks for stamping was already well-liked in India since ancient times. One of the earliest examples of such exchange is the introduction of woodblock printing to India by Buddhist monks from Central Asia. This technique of woodblock print was used to produce religious texts and images. Which were then disseminated throughout the region. The arrival of the Portuguese, Dutch, English, and French in the 16th and 17th centuries brought significant European influence to Indian printmaking. The colonial powers introduced new printing techniques like etching and engraving, which greatly influenced the development of printmaking in India (Mitter 123). European missionaries and traders built printing presses, which facilitated the diffusion of printed products such as books, pamphlets, and pictures in numerous Indian languages. The cultural interaction between the East and the West was extremely important for the spread of knowledge and ideas.

The initial printing press was established in Goa around 1556, courtesy of the Christian Missionaries. This press were actually on their way to Abyssinia to help with missionary work. But due to unavoidable circumstances, the ship detained in Goa which contributed in the rise of printmaking. Primarily the press has been used for religious texts and later British missionaries and colonial administrations used the press for educational and administrative purposes (Goyal and Garima Jain 1).

One of the most notable examples of cross-cultural artistic synthesis has been The Company School of Art, which dates back to late 18th and early 19th century. During this era, traditional themes were blended with European artistic techniques. Particularly in watercolors and lithography, this reflected a unique cultural confluence. Prints from this School played an important role in shaping the visual aesthetics of the colonial period and also contributed to the evolution of modern Indian art (Mitter 94). By the late 1880s, the arrival of popular European prints especially German chromolithographs featuring erotic themes began to take over indigenous art markets. Chromolithography with its bright color reproduction, Chromolithography quickly gained popularity over traditional monochrome lithographs. Indian printing press voluntarily adopted this technique, mainly in urban centres such as Bombay and Pune in Maharashtra, and Calcutta (now Kolkata) in West Bengal. Which have emerged as significant centres of commercial and artistic print production. The 19th century saw the further modernization of Indian printmaking with the introduction of new techniques such as chromolithography and photography. This innovation allowed greater precision and detail in prints, which made printmaking accessible to a broader range of individuals.

One of the most well-known figures in the modernisation of Indian printmaking was Raja Ravi Varma (1894). He established the first Indian printing press in Ghatkopar, Mumbai, known as Ravi Verma Fine Art Lithography Press. The early chromolithograph prints were mainly reproductions of artworks of Raja Ravi Verma for example; Shakuntala Janam (The Birth of Shakuntala) trailed by popular prints depicting deities such as Lakshmi and Saraswati. And also commissioned images were designed to depict religious figures, historical events, nationalist icons, and scenes from mythology and literary classics. Prepared in a distinctive hybrid naturalistic style, these prints mix Western

academic realism with Indian visual sensibilities. Contributing significantly to the formation of a mass visual culture in colonial India.

Raja Ravi Varma's press was an important element in making art accessible to the broader public. Before this, these visual representations of deities and mythological scenes were confined to temple murals or manuscripts, accessible only to the elite. Lithography helped in the mass reproduction of images, allowing them to be accessible to people from various social classes so that they can own and worship these divine representations in their homes. Moreover, the availability of such prints helped nurture a sense of shared national and cultural identity among Indians under British rule. Raja Ravi Varma's work also influenced other Indian artists and printmakers, helping the evolution of regional printing presses and popular visual media in cities like, Calcutta and Madras. The legacy of Ravi Varma's press plays an essential role in Indian visual culture, connecting the bridge between traditional narratives and modern techniques and democratizing the art experience.

Santiniketan, founded by Rabindranath Tagore (1861) in the early 20th century, has been intended as more than just an educational institution. Santiniketan has been a philosophical and cultural experiment hub, aimed at creating a complete learning environment rooted in humanistic values and global exchange. Under Visva-Bharati University, Tagore sought to bridge the gap between Eastern spiritual traditions, Western scientific and artistic advancements, fostering a space where art was not limited by geographic or ideological boundaries. (Mitter 1530).

Santiniketan emerged as a vessel for global modernism in India. Artists like Nandalal Bose, Benode Behari Mukherjee and Somnath Hore have been influence by open dialogue and cross-cultural engagement. These artists used Western printmaking techniques with

indigenous materials and themes derived from Indian folk traditions, mythology, and rural life. Various elements of Japanese woodblock printing, Chinese ink painting, and Western composition have been reflected in the work Nandalal Bose (1882). On the other hand, Somnath Hore (1921), used intaglio and dry point techniques for producing powerful prints that responded to social-political events like the Bengal Famine and Vietnam War infusing modernist form with deeply humanistic and political content. (Kapur 67).

At the beginning of the 20th century, there were changes in the aesthetic preferences of the public, leading to the emergence of a group of artists who sought to create a new Indian aesthetic. This new aesthetic has been referred to as the evolving and diverse artistic movements in India reflecting the change of times and the developing cultural landscapes of the country. The new Indian aesthetic has also changed the values and beliefs of the people, and the artists to express their unique creativity. The occurrence of this new Indian aesthetic was a significant milestone in the history of Indian art and culture (Mago 211). Hence the beginning of the 20th century started distinguishing between printing and printmaking which have become increasingly distinct identities. As a creative process, printmaking has evolved to encompass a variety of techniques and styles, from traditional woodblock printing to digital printing. It has become a medium of expression for many artists, allowing them to create unique works of art that are both visually striking and meaningful (Goel and Singh 150).

The impact of globalisation on printmaking in India has been both significant and multifaceted. Globalisation has opened up new opportunities for Indian printmakers to engage with international markets and utilise advanced technologies (Goel and Singh 153). However, it has presented challenges to traditional methods and materials that have long used in the art form. Globalisation has also acted as a platform for Indian printmakers, which provides them access to a broader audience and increased exposure to

international art markets. This exposure has allowed them to showcase their work on a global scale and connect with collectors and galleries from around the world (Gupta 89). Also advancements in technology have made it easier for Indian printmakers to collaborate with artists and printmakers from different countries, leading to the exchange of ideas and techniques.

Globalisation has greatly benefited Indian printmakers by providing them with opportunities to expand their reach and connect with a global audience. With the help of international exhibitions, art fairs, and online platforms, Indian printmakers have able to showcase their work to a wide audience and attract potential buyers from around the world (Goel and Singh 154). This has not only increased their visibility but also allowed them to establish valuable connections within the international art community.

International exhibitions have played a crucial role in promoting Indian printmakers on a global scale. Events like these provide a platform for artists to display their work alongside their international counterparts, allowing for cross-cultural exchange and appreciation (Dalmia 178). The exposure gained from participating in such exhibitions has proven as instrumental in attracting the attention of art enthusiasts and collectors from different part of the world. These platforms not only raise the status of Indian printmaking but also inspire artists to experiment and improve their techniques (Mago 216). Participation of artists around the world leads to collaborative projects, residencies, and invitations to global art fairs. These types of opportunities help integrate Indian printmakers into the broader narrative of contemporary art.

One of the most prominent examples is Biennale Printmaking or Print Biennial, an international exhibition that happens every two years and focuses on printmaking. This event often showcase a diverse range of printmaking techniques and styles, including

traditional processes such as woodcut, etching, and lithography, as well as more contemporary techniques such as digital printmaking and 3D printing (Lalit Kala Akademi; Goel and Singh 155). Event includes the work of artists from all over the world, providing a forum for them to communicate, cooperate, and share their work with a larger audience. These events may also include workshops, talks, and other educational activities that aims at promoting the art and technique of printmaking (Dalmia 182).

The Lalit Kala Akademi hosted the first-ever International Print Biennale in New Delhi, with a record number of 17 countries taking part in it. Is the first-ever International Exhibition of Graphic Prints ‘Print Biennale India 2018’ opened on 25th March at the Rabindra Bhavan Galleries of the Lalit Kala Akademi in New Delhi. The goal of such an event was to explore new artistic trends in printmaking on a national and worldwide scale, as well as to explore new ideas (Lalit Kala Akademi). And there is also, Kochi-Muziris Biennale, which was held in the Indian state of Kerela.

Another international creative event took place at Rothko Museum on 8th-22nd March 2024, which invited artists to participate in the ‘12th International Latgale Graphic Art Symposium’. It was the most significant international event in the graphic medium. Over the years, this creative forum has brought together over a hundred graphic artists from 34 countries. The emergence of art galleries and collectives has also become significant avenues for Indian printmakers to showcase their talent and gain recognition. These types of events bring together a diverse range of artists, galleries, and collectors, providing a unique opportunity for Indian printmakers can engage with potential buyers, discuss their artistic process, and forge collaborations that can lead to further opportunities for exposure and growth (Lalit Kala Akademi; Goel and Singh 155).

In recent years, Indian printmakers have collaborated with artists from other nations in novel and creative ways. These collaborations produce a diverse range of prints, from traditional woodblock prints to experimental digital prints. One of the most prominent partnerships is a current initiative between Indian and Japanese printmakers. A project, supported by the Japanese government, seeks to foster cultural interchange and collaboration between the two nations (JapanFoundation). As part of the project, Indian and Japanese artists collaborated to make prints that included aspects from both cultures. The resulting prints were distinctive and represent many influences that formed Indian printing (Gupta 96).

Exhibitions and workshops have also become significant avenues for Indian printmakers to showcase their talent and gain recognition. They provide a hands-on opportunity for artists to learn new techniques and methods from other artist. When artists from different cultural backgrounds come together in a workshop, they not only learn from the instructor but also from one another, sharing their unique perspectives and approaches towards the artistry. Through exhibitions and workshops, artists get exposed to diverse artistic traditions, both within India and from other countries. This type of exposure can lead to the incorporation of new elements into their work, enriching the Indian printmaking scene with a broader range of influences and styles. These exposures are important for professional networking as they provide opportunities for artists to meet and connect with other artists, curators, collectors, and art enthusiasts. These connections can lead to collaborations, further exposure, and opportunities for growth and development in the field of printmaking. On the whole, exhibits and workshops act as an important part in promoting cross-cultural influences in Indian printing by offering forums for discourse, skill sharing, exposure to other creative traditions, cultural exchange, and professional networking.

The impact of globalisation on printmaking in India is a topic of significant. This has undeniably opened up new avenues for Indian artists to showcase their work on a global platform. This type of exposure has facilitated the adoption of modern technological tools and techniques, thereby enhancing the quality and reach of Indian printmaking.

However, it is important to acknowledge the challenges that globalisation has brought to traditional printmaking practices in India. Emergence of new materials and methods has posed a threat to the authenticity and essence of the ancient techniques that have defined Indian printmaking for generations. Maintaining a balance by preserving these traditions and embracing innovation is paramount to sustaining the growth and relevance of printmaking in India.

Cross-cultural expression plays a key role in recognising global understanding, creativity, and unity, but it also has its own set of challenges. One of the main concerns is the use of elements of one culture, may be used without proper understanding or respect and can lead to stereotyping, misrepresentation, or the loss of cultural authenticity. This can especially take place when a traditional practice is used for commercial or entertainment purposes. Language barriers and power imbalances between dominant and marginalised cultures complicate these exchanges even more. For preserving the richness and integrity of diverse cultures throughout countries, it is important to support community-led representation, promote cultural education, and encourage collaboration. Putting efforts in documenting traditional knowledge, protecting Indigenous rights, and supporting respectful dialogue can help ensure that cross-cultural expression remains a source of connection rather than division.

To sum up, printmaking in India is a rich and diverse art form moulded by cross-cultural influences throughout the centuries. In which globalisation has played a vital role in

introducing new techniques and styles to the art form, there is a significant focus on preserving and honouring traditional methods, materials, and indigenous practices that form the foundation of India's printmaking legacy. Contemporary artists from every country are actively playing a part in this blend of the old and the new offering to revive ancient techniques such as woodcuts, etching, and lithography while experimenting with digital media and mixed media forms. This constant fusion has given rise to a vibrant and dynamic printmaking culture that is unique in India, yet globally relevant. Cross-culture exchange maintain a deep respect for the past while embracing the future, resulting in an art form that continues to thrive, adapt, and inspire both within India and on the international stage.

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